

**RE.
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PURPOSE AND SCOPE OF THE PILOT PLAN

The Pilot Plan is the first Deliverable of WP4 “Deployment and Operation” of the RECAP project. Its purpose is to provide Pilot partners with the necessary guidance, tools and methodology for successfully organizing and deploying the testing and validation of the RECAP Platform (Pilot) in an operational environment in the five pilot countries. The Pilot in RECAP is however, not only conceived for demonstration purposes, but it also aims at proving the feasibility and added value of the uptake scenarios of the RECAP solution in different operational settings. Hence, the Pilot will include an evaluation of the satisfaction of the end-users with the RECAP solution in order to determine to which extent the RECAP solution meets the objectives initially defined. This evaluation will also allow gathering effective feedback to enhance the RECAP platform prior to its commercial exploitation and will also allow drawing recommendations on the future use of this approach to deliver more effective and efficient public administration.

The information, tools and procedures included in the Pilot Plan will allow for:

- **Maximization of end-user participation**, including identification, involvement and engagement of end-users and other stakeholders, in order to achieve the impact indicators as stated in the Grant Agreement while ensuring their satisfactory participation,
- **Optimization of partner resources**, including the definition of a project team, required use of internal staff, equipment and facilities needed, etc.
- **Coordination of Pilot deployment**, covering all organizational aspects from training to specific logistics and timing of the Pilots, taking into account partner resources, end-user specificities and Pilot scenarios,
- **Definition of an effective monitoring system**, including an internal communication system among Pilot partners, Pilot coordinator, technical desk and project coordinator in order to ensure a smooth implementation of the Pilots, the monitoring of activities, the early identification of potential problems and the implementation of the respective contingency measures,
- **Definition of an effective evaluation system** of the RECAP solution by end-users, ensuring the feedback obtained is reliable and allows for enhancing the RECAP platform in view of its market exploitation, as well as the drawing of recommendations and policy support scenarios.
- **Setting up a procedure for future applications of the RECAP platform** by public organisations and agricultural consultants, thus ensuring its transferability and wider take-up. This will be further developed in Deliverable 4.5 “Report on procedures followed and lessons learnt”.

The Pilot (WP4) is central to the project as it will test the RECAP solution developed in WP3 (also through the co-production task conducted in 2.4) and its results will feed the Business Model task in WP5. The success of the Pilot therefore requires of **the close coordination of the Pilot** with task 2.4 and WP3 upstream and WP5 downstream in order to ensure that the RECAP project objectives are being achieved. Collaboration between the partners involved in these WPs (UREAD, WP2 leader, DRAXIS, WP3 leader, ETAM, WP5 leader and INI, WP4 leader) has taken place through several Skype meetings during the month of March and April and a specific session on the Pilot at the 3rd project meeting in Pamplona in April 2017.

In order to facilitate the organisation of the Pilot and a more straight forward deployment of activities, the overall work has been divided into three separate phases, each with a different set of activities, procedures, tools and actors involved:

- **Pre-Pilot phase:** this phase encompasses the preparatory work needed for a proper execution of the pilot. Activities include the definition of a project team in the Pilot organisations, the setting up of internal procedures for Pilot development, monitoring and evaluation, the installation and testing of the RECAP platform in the different devices, as well as the recruitment of participants.
- **Pilot Phase:** this phase encompasses the testing and validation of the RECAP Platform (actual Pilot) in an operational environment in the five pilot countries. Activities include the setting up of the proper coordination and communication strategies, the setting up of the technical support, the training of participants, the testing of the different modules of the RECAP platform by the end-users and the monitoring of the Pilot activities.
- **Post-Pilot Phase:** this phase encompasses the closure of the Pilot. Activities include evaluation of the Pilot, production of D4.4 (Final Evaluation Report) and D4.5 (Report on procedures followed and lessons learnt) and input of information to WP5 (Business models and operational perspective).

The present Pilot Plan is structured as follows:

- **Chapter 1** presents an overview of the Pilot, describing the objectives, target outcomes, expected impact, geographical coverage and partners involved, Pilot scenarios, an overview of the monitoring and evaluation as well as an overview of the different phases of the Pilot.
- **Chapter 2** presents the Monitoring and Evaluation procedure of the RECAP Pilot, including methodology and tools.
- **Chapters 3, 4 and 5** present respectively and in detail the Pre-Pilot, Pilot and Post-Pilot phases as described above.
- **Chapter 6** presents in detail the different Pilot Cases (scenarios) in the project countries, including the timeframe of the Pilot in each country.

The Balance Score Card with the battery of Key Performance Indicators defined for the monitoring and evaluation procedure of the pilot is presented as an Annex to the Pilot Plan. As the Pilot is deployed, other supporting documents and forms will be produced according to the needs of pilot partners. Among others, the following documents will be produced: template for recruitment mailing, informed consent form for participants, guidelines for the organization of the training sessions, attendance sheets for the training sessions, evaluation questionnaires and guidelines for the organisation of focus groups.

1. OVERVIEW OF THE PILOT IN RECAP

1.1. Objectives, outcomes and expected impact of the pilots

1.1.1 Objectives of the Pilot in the frame of the RECAP project

The overall objective of RECAP is to develop and test a platform for the delivery of public services that will enable the improved implementation of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). RECAP integrates open and user-generated data into added value services, co-designed, and co-created by public authorities, farmers, and agricultural consultants. In particular, RECAP aims at:

- Increasing efficiency and transparency of public authorities responsible for the implementation of the CAP, by allowing improved remote monitoring of obligations of farmers through the use of open and user-generated data,
- Offering personalised services to farmers for better compliance with the environmental standards imposed by the CAP,
- Stimulating the development of new added value services by agricultural consultants and developers who will create add-ons to the main platform and make use of the data collected.

Within RECAP, WP4 “Deployment and Operation” encompasses the Pilot testing and validation of the RECAP services in an operational environment in five countries (Spain, Greece, Lithuania, UK and Serbia) with the participation of end-users. The Pilot implementation in Spain, Greece, and Lithuania will focus on the public service delivery, with the participation of four public organisations, which are members of the project consortium (INTIA, OPEKEPE, NMA, and LAAS) and responsible for the implementation of the CAP in these countries. In UK and Serbia, the delivery of personalised services will be tested with private companies that offer agricultural consultancy services (STRUTT & PARKER and INO respectively).

The usability, effectiveness and impact of the RECAP services in delivering the public administrations' goals will also be evaluated in the frame of WP4, through the assessment of the satisfaction levels of end-users (public organisations, agricultural consultants and farmers) with the RECAP services. Questionnaires, focus groups as well as the measurement of a set of Key Performance Indicators, will allow determining to what extent the RECAP solution reduces administrative cost for public authorities and administrative burden for farmers. Thus, the evaluation of the Pilots is expected to provide recommendations on the future use of this approach to deliver more effective and efficient public administration.

To this end, WP4 “Deployment and Operation” has the following specific objectives:

- To establish a detailed pilot plan to guide the effective and successful deployment of RECAP in 5 pilot countries,
- To identify all training needs for the pilot and complete training within each country in accordance with those needs,
- To successfully install the solution and perform the pilot testing in 5 locations: Spain, Greece, Lithuania, UK, and Serbia, with the active participation of 4 public authorities and 2 agricultural consultants which are included in the RECAP consortium, and farmers as end users,
- To monitor the effective conduct of the Pilots, and provide an effective feedback mechanism to enhance the solution,
- To evaluate the extent to which RECAP is meeting the overall objectives established for the solution.

1.1.2 Outcomes and expected impacts

The outcomes of the Pilot will contribute to the achievement of the strategic impacts of the RECAP project, namely: the stimulation of the creation, delivery and use of new services coupled with open public data; the delivery of more personalised public services that better suit the needs of users; the reduction of the administrative burden of citizens and businesses and the increased transparency of and trust in public administrations. The achievement of the impacts will be measured through the monitoring of a set of result and impact indicators, as shown in the table below:

Table 1. Result and Impact Indicators for the Pilots

Indicator	Measurement technique	Total target value
Number of farmers* in pilots	Demonstration in 5 pilot sites	635
Number of cross compliance inspections carried out remotely with RECAP	Demonstration in 5 pilot sites	305
Number of on the spot checks carried out with RECAP	Demonstration (RECAP vs Business As usual Scenarios) in 5 pilot sites	115
Reduction of administrative cost for payment agencies	Demonstration (RECAP vs Business As usual Scenarios) in 5 pilot sites – Evaluation of Results	>25%
Reduction of administrative burden for farmers	Demonstration (RECAP vs Business As usual Scenarios) in 5 pilot sites – Evaluation of Results	>25%

**As per discussions among Pilot partners and RECAP coordinator during the 3rd Consortium meeting in April in Pamplona, this target value can be equated to “CAP claims”, as a single farmer can have many independent CAP claims.*

A monitoring and evaluation system will be put in place in order to ensure the timely and proper development of the Pilots so as to achieve the expected outcomes. This system will also allow determining whether the above mentioned result and impact indicators have been achieved. The monitoring and evaluation system is presented in detail in Chapter 2.

1.1.3 Coordination with co-production phase and Business Plan development

The Pilot (WP4) is central to the project as it will test the RECAP solution developed in WP3 (also through the co-production work conducted in WP2) and its results will give valuable information to feed the Business Model task in WP5. As mentioned above, collaboration between the partners involved in these WPs (UREAD, WP2 leader, DRAXIS, WP3 leader, ETAM, WP5 leader and INI, WP4 leader) has taken place during the preparation of the Pilot Plan. This has allowed for a more targeted definition of the issues subject to evaluation and will permit a smooth transition of activities between WPs as well as the avoidance of unnecessary overlaps.

The partners involved in this transition have worked on the definition of the platform features to evaluate in the Pilots, as this information will on the one hand, allow WP3 to tweak the RECAP platform prior to its commercial exploitation, and on the other hand, feed valuable information to the development of the most suitable Business Model for the RECAP solution. Similarly, as end-users were involved in the co-production phase (WP2), partners deemed necessary that roughly the same features worked upon in the co-production phase are evaluated in the Pilot, so that end-users feel their contribution was valuable and their inputs were taken into consideration for the development of the RECAP solution. Partners also agreed that some of the same end-users involved in the co-production phase were also to be involved in the Pilot, as involving the

same set of end-users in the whole process of production, testing and evaluation of the RECAP solution will increase their engagement in the project and result in their acting as ambassadors for recruiting other participants, also allowing for a smooth development of the pilots.

The development of a first version of the evaluation questionnaires will be conducted collaboratively among WP2 leader (UREAD), WP4 leader (INI) and WP5 leader (ETAM), between May and September 2017. A second version of the questionnaires will be produced at a later stage (winter 2017).

1.2. Geographical coverage, partners involved and end-users

The RECAP platform will be tested and validated in an operational environment in five countries (Spain, Greece, Lithuania, UK and Serbia), with the active participation of public organisations, agricultural consultants and farmers as end-users of the RECAP service.

RECAP partners involved in the Pilot are INTIA (Spain), OPEKEPE (Greece), NMA and LAAS (Lithuania), STRUTT & PARKER (UK) and INO (Serbia). The Pilot implementation in Spain, Greece, and Lithuania will focus on the public service delivery, with the participation of four public organisations, which are members of the project consortium (INTIA, OPEKEPE, NMA, and LAAS). In UK and Serbia, the delivery of personalised services will be tested with private companies that offer agricultural consultancy services (STRUTT & PARKER and INO respectively). Details on the different scenarios in each of the piloting countries are presented in Chapter 6.

End-users, such as farmers, farmers' associations and cooperatives will be involved in all pilots. Their participation will be entirely voluntary and the RECAP partners will obtain their informed consent in advance. A detailed plan for end-user involvement in each of the pilot countries is presented in Chapter 6.

INI acts as WP4 leader and is in charge of the design of the Pilot Plan, the necessary tools and templates for Pilot implementation, the coordination of the Pilots in the five countries, the monitoring and evaluation of the Pilot development and the production of the deliverables in WP4.

DRAXIS and NOA will support the technical implementation of the pilot by conducting the following activities: validation of the Training Guides (D4.2), support for the installation of the RECAP platform in the different devices in close coordination with the ICT specialist in each pilot organisation, technical support to the ICT specialist during the pilot development.

1.3. Pilot deployment: overview of the phases and calendar

WP4 "Pilot Deployment and Operation" in RECAP will take place over a period of 15 months, starting in Month 16 and finishing in Month 30, hence spanning half of the lifetime of the project. As mentioned in the Preface, the overall work has been divided into three separate phases, each with a different set of activities, procedures, tools and actors involved, aiming at facilitating the organisation of the Pilot as a whole. Figure 1 shows the Pre-Pilot, Pilot and Post-Pilot phases and the activities included in each phase. A complete description is presented in detail in Chapters 3, 4 and 5.

Figure 1. Activities included in the Pre-pilot, pilot and post-pilot phases

The three phases will be developed subsequently during the whole duration of WP4. A preliminary calendar for the development of the three phases is shown in Figure 2. Given the different scenarios covered in the five pilot countries imply the involvement of different end-users this calendar may be changed by partners in order to better match their scenario. Details on the different pilot scenarios are presented in Chapter 6.

Calendar of the Pre-Pilot, Pilot and Post-Pilot phases	2017						2018									
	J	A	S	O	N	D	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O
	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30
PRE-PILOT																
1. Setting up of local team																
2. Setting up of internal procedures																
3. Recruitment of participants																
PILOT																
1. Pilot coordination, communication and technical support																
2. Training of participants																
3. Use of the RECAP platform (depending on country)																
4. Monitoring and Reporting																
POST-PILOT																
1. Evaluation of the Pilot																
2. Exploitation and sustainability of pilot results																
3. Procedures followed and lessons learnt																

Figure 2. Tentative calendar of the activities included in the Pre-pilot, pilot and post-pilot phases

1.4. Risk assessment and contingency plan

Risk assessment of the Pilot will follow the procedures set in the risk and contingency plan of the RECAP project. It will aim at ensuring that the Pilot objectives are achieved in spite of negative events occurring during the course of the Pilot. The potential problems encountered during the Pilot will be analysed, described, classified and managed within the WP4 team, following the internal communication procedures described in section 1.5.

Risk identification and assessment will be performed in a systematic fashion throughout the development of the Pilot. Monitoring of the Pilot progress through the measurement of the Key Performance Indicators and informal frequent communication with partners will be key activities that will allow for an early identification of risks. The WP4 team will establish risk mitigation plans to reduce the likelihood of the risks occurring and their impact, as well as action plans to manage the consequences of the risk, should it materialize. The WP4 leader will be in close coordination with the project coordinator in order to revise and update the Risk Management Report.

At the stage of proposal writing, major risk areas were identified and contingency measures developed to avoid or mitigate situations that could hamper the successful completion of the project objectives. The risks identified and contingency measures proposed for WP4 are shown in the table below.

Table 2. Risks identified and contingency measures proposed for the Pilot

Risk identified	Contingency measure proposed
Participation of end users in the pilot is low	Three measures have been adopted: i) tailoring of the dissemination strategy of the project for encouraging end-user participation (section 1.5); ii) engagement of the same set of end-users in the pilot as in the co-production phase in order for them to act as ambassadors and attract other end-users; iii) inclusion of the recommendations of participants in the co-production phase in the RECAP platform in order to make them feel valued so that they motivate other end-users.
Farmers are reluctant to participate in pilots because they are concerned about the use of data provided	The informed consent form includes a contractual guarantee by which the data collected through the pilot tests will not be used for control and penalty purposes in the framework of cross-compliance or other obligations imposed by CAP
Evaluation questionnaires are not effective and end-users have difficulties in responding	Questionnaires will be initially tested with a small group of pilot users (preferably those who participated in the co-production phase) for comprehension and completeness. If this first small round reveals problems or deficiencies, questionnaires will be redesigned before opening the process to the wider end-user groups.
Data generated from farmers by using the RECAP mobile application toolkit is of low quality	Quality assurance/Quality control (QA/QC) of data is one of the critical components of the project, to provide data of known quality. This will be achieved through the development and implementation of a data QA/QC plan. In addition, the assessment of data uncertainty may need to be implemented in parallel with QA/QC plan, to improve data accuracy and reduce uncertainty.
Disruption in Sentinel data procurement	Sentinel-1 archive data will be used instead. For optical data, exploitation of third-parties mission (Copernicus Contributing Missions) data & Landsat 8.

This table will be updated as the Pilot develops. Contingency measures will be agreed upon by the WP4 leader and the RECAP project coordinator.

1.5. Communication in the frame of the Pilot

1.5.1. Internal communication

Internal communication within the Pilot will be in line with the internal communication strategy at the overall project level. Fluent communication between WP4 leader (INI) and RECAP coordinator (DRAXIS) will be established in order to address potential risks, assess progress of activities and ensure the achievement of the pilot objectives. The WP4 leader will be responsible to ensure a smooth and efficient internal communication among Pilot participants, project coordinator and WP4 leader.

Formal internal communication will include: i) “pilot update” emails on a monthly basis, compiling the information on the current progress of work of the Pilots in the different countries and recommendations for the proper development of the activities; ii) three pre-scheduled Skype meetings with each of the Pilot partners during the development of the Pilot: as part of the preparatory work, half-way and one month prior to end date. Skype meetings will be documented in writing; both the agenda and minutes will be readily available for all interested partners. It is foreseeable that further Skype meetings will be needed along the Pilot development. Pilot partners shall be able to call for a Skype meeting with WP4 leader in their free will.

1.5.2. External communication

External communication of the activities conducted within the Pilot will be in line with the external communication strategy at the overall project level; it should follow its procedures and use the available tools. Partners shall report to the Dissemination Manager, the WP4 leader and the project Coordinator any communication activity conducted during the pilot.

External communication activities should be tailored to the specific phase of the pilot (pre-pilot, pilot and post-pilot), given that objectives, target groups and tools should be different. Detailed information on the external communication features for each of the pilot phases is presented in the corresponding sections (Chapters 3, 4 and 5).

2. MONITORING AND EVALUATION OF THE RECAP PILOT

2.1. Objectives of the Monitoring and Evaluation Plan

A Monitoring and Evaluation Plan will be set in place with the following objectives:

- Measure the progress of the work in the Pilot, determining the accomplishment of intermediate deadlines and key milestones for a satisfactory development of the Pilot,
- Function as an early warning mechanism, allowing to identify potential problems in the RECAP platform or in the Pilot approach,
- Determine the achievement of the overall Pilot goals in terms of end-user involvement and satisfaction, Pilot and project outcomes and impact of the RECAP solution in end-users and other stakeholders,
- Determine the sustainability of the RECAP platform in order for it to transition into a sustainable and operational service, in close coordination with WP5 “Exploitation”,
- Provide insights for the future applications of the RECAP platform by public organisations and agricultural consultants in order to ensure the transferability and wider take-up of the platform.
- Draw recommendations about the project implementation and its results and policy support scenarios.

The Monitoring and Evaluation Plan will use the internal communication system set up for the Pilot execution among the Pilot coordinator, the Pilot partners and the RECAP coordinator for the compilation of the information required. Fluent communication between WP4 leader (INI) and RECAP coordinator (DRAXIS) will be established in order to manage potential delays and/or problems in Pilot Implementation. Details on the internal communication and coordination of the Pilots as well as risk management have been presented in Chapter 1.

2.2. Tools and methodology for the Monitoring and Evaluation

2.2.1. Quantitative tools:

The Monitoring and Evaluation Plan is in line with the monitoring procedures set up at the overall project level by the RECAP coordinator (D1.1). The set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) defined at the outset of the project for WP4 has been expanded, defining a battery of KPIs that includes more specific indicators related to the different phases of the Pilot and the activities to be conducted in each phase, as well as other output, outcome/result and impact indicators. This has been made so as to obtain more complete and broken-down information to tackle the development of the Pilot in the five countries as well as to obtain relevant inputs for the evaluation of the RECAP solution, its sustainability and future applications.

Indicators have been chosen so they meet the standards of good indicators (SMART): Specific, Measurable, Available/Achievable in a cost effective way, Relevant for the project, and Timely available. Different types of indicators are used:

- **Output indicators:** they measure activities directly carried out within the Pilot, as a first step towards realising its overall goals. They allow determining the progress of work and act as a first-level warning for potential problems (e.g. problems in the installation of the RECAP platform).
- **Outcome/result indicators:** they measure the direct and immediate effects of the activities, which will contribute to the achievement of the specific objectives of the Pilot. They act as a second-level warning for potential problems (e.g. low end-user involvement in Pilots).
- **Impact indicators:** they measure the impact of the Pilot in the frame of the project and are related to its broader objectives (e.g. reduction of administrative burden for farmers).

In order to facilitate KPIs monitoring, the indicators have been broken-down by partner and category (see Annex). This will facilitate information delivery by partners, as each partner will be asked to complete the indicators related to its tasks and activities in which it is involved. Information analysis at different levels will also be eased, allowing for greater visibility of the situation to-date, the progress made, and a faster detection of possible deviations.

Output and outcome/result indicators will be readily gathered by partners as the work in the different phases of the Pilot progresses. In the case of impact indicators, information for the update of the KPIs will be gathered by partners through questionnaires completed by Pilot participants as well as qualitative information gathered in the Focus Groups.

The BSC will be updated by the WP4 coordinator at the relevant milestones of the Pilot execution in each of the countries, but, as a minimum every two months during pilot development (see Section 2.3 on reporting). The updated BSC will be shared with the project coordinator.

2.2.2. *Qualitative tools:*

Qualitative tools (questionnaires and focus groups) will be used in order to gather the following information:

- Degree of satisfaction of end-users with the RECAP platform, covering features worked upon in the co-production phase but also other features considered of interest by WP3 leader for the tweaking of the platform,
- Degree of accomplishment of the impact indicators of the project (e.g. decrease in the administrative burden),
- User perceptions, potential demand of the RECAP platform in the Pilot countries, inputs regarding price and purchase of the service, insights for future applications and sustainability of the RECAP platform, transferability issues, etc,
- End-users views that allow drawing recommendations in the areas covered by the project as well as policy support scenarios.

2.2.2.1. *Questionnaires*

A set of questionnaires will be designed in order to cover the different aspects of the evaluation according to the specific end-user group (farmers, inspectors from Paying Agencies and agricultural consultants). The questionnaires will be filled in by end-users upon testing of the relevant functionality or module of the RECAP platform (e.g. inspectors of paying agencies should fill in the questionnaire after they complete the report stage, see calendar in section 6.3). Questionnaires will be self-administered (e.g. through the use of Google forms or other on-line tool) and they will use numeric or graphic scale-rating for facilitating analysis.

Different response targets have been set according to the total number of end-users participating in the Pilots (see BSC for details), but Pilot partners should always aim at maximizing response rate.

2.2.2.2. Focus groups

Focus groups will be organized in order to validate the survey findings as well as to obtain insights on the usefulness and potential for exploitation and sustainability of the RECAP platform. It will also allow identifying policy support scenarios and issuing recommendations on the basis of end-users needs. As the focus group methodology also allows obtaining “hidden” or unconscious information, it will be of great value as an input to the Business Plan.

One focus group will be organized with each of the end-user groups at the end of the Pilot. As far as possible, partners should seek to involve at least one or two of the individuals that participated in the co-production phase and the Pilot, in order for them to see end-to-end the development process of the RECAP platform and feel their views have been included in the production of the final platform.

A group between 8-12 participants should be aimed for. Focus groups will be facilitated by staff in the Pilot partner organisation. Preferably, the facilitator will have experience in semi-structured interviews with similar groups of end-users. Ideally, it will be the same person having facilitated the workshops in the consultation phase (see D2.2). The sessions will be tape-recorded and transcripts will be produced afterwards for further analysis.

Questions to be discussed at the focus group will be determined upon careful analysis of the results of the questionnaires by the WP4 leader in collaboration with task 2.4 leader (UREAD), RECAP coordinator and WP5 leader (ETAM). Final questions will be tested with the same set of end-users that participated throughout the process prior to their use in the focus group. The final procedure for the Focus Groups and instructions on how to conduct them will be produced in a separate document from the Pilot Plan at least 1 month prior to the organization of the first focus groups.

2.3. Reporting

Reporting on the progress of the work by Pilot partners will be requested by the WP4 leader in order to ensure the smooth implementation of the Pilot, the identification of potential risks and the definition of contingency measures. Reporting will be done formally by three means:

- Feedback from Pilot partners to WP4 leader and Project coordinator upon the “Pilot update” email sent by WP4 leader bimonthly;
- Pilot Implementation Report on a pre-defined template twice during Pilot progress and in connection with the project internal progress reports sent to the project coordinator. Tentatively, the reporting calendar for the Pilots will be as follows: Month 21 (2 months prior to the delivery of D4.3 Intermediate Evaluation and Adaptation report) and Month 29 (1 month prior to delivery of D4.4. “Final Evaluation Report”). The Pilot Implementation Report shall cover the main activities carried out, problems and delays encountered and the corrective actions taken. The Pilot Implementation Report in Month 29 will also include the report on the evaluation activities. WP4 leader will produce both the Intermediate and Final Evaluation Reports with the input of Pilot partners and the collaboration of WP2 and WP5 leaders.
- Progress of the work will be presented by Pilot partners in the consortium meetings to be organized during the duration of the Pilot (M18-M30), which are planned for Months 19 and 25.

Informal contact between WP4 leader and pilot partners will ensure early identification of potential problems and the implementation of contingency measures, as described in Section 1.4.

2.4. Time plan for the implementation of the monitoring and evaluation system

The final time plan for the deployment of the evaluation procedure will be agreed upon once the final schedule of the Pilots is decided upon by each of the Pilot partners. A tentative calendar is presented in Figure 3.

Calendar of the monitoring and evaluation system	2017						2018									
	J	A	S	O	N	D	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O
	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30
MONITORING																
1. Agreement on KPIs and methodology																
2. KPI monitoring in connection with "pilot update"																
3. Pilot progress review at project meeting																
4. Partners Pilot Implementation Report																
5. Intermediate evaluation report																
EVALUATION																
1. Agreement on methodology																
2. First draft of questionnaires																
3. Questionnaires (depending on country)																
4. Focus Groups (depending on country)																
5. Pilot progress review at project meeting																
6. Partners Pilot Implementation Report with evaluation																
7. Final evaluation report																

Figure 3. Tentative calendar of the implementation of the monitoring and evaluation system.

3. PREPARATORY WORK OF THE RECAP PILOT (PRE-PILOT)

Chapter 3 gives a detailed overview of the preparatory work needed for a proper execution of the Pilot and that will take place prior to the actual deployment of the Pilot. The preparatory work involves the following:

- Appointment of a local team in the Pilot organisation,
- Setting up of internal procedures for Pilot development, including coordination, communication, technical support, translation of documents, definition of time plan and installation of the platform,
- Recruitment of participants.

A summary of the preparatory work to be conducted is presented at the end of the Chapter. The foreseen dates of completion of the preparatory tasks are to be communicated by the pilot partner to the WP4 leader and project coordinator at the consortium meeting in Pamplona (April 28th 2017).

3.1. Appointment of a local team in the Pilot organisation

Each Pilot organization will set up a local team in charge of implementing the Pilot. In general, the staff at the Pilot organisations that participate in the RECAP project will also participate in the Pilot. The roles to be covered by staff in the team are:

- **Pilot coordinator:** she/he will oversee the correct development of the different phases of the Pilot. She/he will act as the contact point of the Pilot organisation with WP4 leader and RECAP coordinator and will be in charge of reporting on the progress of the Pilot and evaluating its impact.
- **Facilitator:** she/he will be responsible for the correct development of the training sessions and the focus groups in the evaluation. She/he can be the same person as the Pilot coordinator.
- **ICT specialist:** she/he will be in charge of the correct installation of the RECAP platform in the different devices and will provide support to Pilot participants with any technical problem that may arise with the platform throughout the Pilot in close coordination with DRAXIS and NOA.

Other staff at the pilot organisation may also be required for support with the following tasks: external communication of the Pilot activities (typically, it will be the same person in charge of communication at the overall project level), recruitment of participants, support to the evaluation of the Pilot (questionnaire processing and organisation and evaluation of focus group).

Table 3. Overview of roles of the local team in the Pilot organization.

Role	Overall coordination	Internal communication	Monitoring	Evaluation	Training	Platform installation	External communication	Recruitment
Coordinator	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓
Facilitator				✓	✓			
ICT specialist					✓	✓		
Other staff			✓	✓	✓		✓	✓

3.2. Setting up of the internal procedures and structures for Pilot development

Pilot partners shall follow the steps presented in the figure below for the setting up of the internal procedures and structures for the Pilot development at each pilot country.

Figure 4. Steps for setting up internal procedures and structures for Pilot development

3.2.1. Setting up of internal coordination and communication procedures

The Pilot coordinator will be in charge of ensuring the proper development of the Pilot activities in the Pilot country for which she/he will set up the necessary internal coordination and communication procedures within the local Pilot team. Frequent meetings among local team members will be programmed at key stages of the Pilot in order to coordinate the work of the Pilot team and ensure the achievement of milestones and Pilot objectives.

The Pilot coordinator will be in charge of monitoring the progress of the Pilot and communicating on it to the WP4 leader and the project coordinator. She/he shall use the internal communication procedure of the RECAP project and the specific tools and procedures made available for monitoring of the Pilot: i) update of the BSC KPIs at the time of the bimonthly “Pilot updates” sent by the WP4 leader; ii) pre-scheduled and ad-hoc Skype meetings when necessary; iii) Pilot progress report. Details of the monitoring procedure have been described in Chapter 2. The Pilot coordinator will also be responsible for flagging any deviation of the defined Pilot plan to the WP4 leader and the project coordinator so that potential risks are addressed with the implementation of ad-hoc contingency measures.

3.2.2. Setting up of technical support procedure

The ICT specialist/s will be in charge of the correct installation of the RECAP platform in the different devices and will provide support to Pilot participants with any technical problem that may arise with the platform throughout the Pilot. She/he shall be in close contact with DRAXIS and NOA, who will act as the technical desk of the Pilot. Communication between the ICT specialist, DRAXIS and NOA shall be made by e-mail and Skype conference when necessary, always including WP4 leader in CC.

The ICT specialist shall act as the first level technical support to Pilot participants in the specific Pilot countries. She/he shall solve any technical issue emerging during the development of the Pilot. Only when the technical issue is of sufficient entity so that it may affect other Pilot countries, or when she/he cannot fix the technical issue at stake, she/he shall raise the issue to the Pilot technical desk (DRAXIS and NOA), who will strive for a quick response in order not to delay the implementation of the Pilot.

As soon as the ICT specialists are appointed, a Skype meeting will be organized with all ICT specialists in the Pilot countries, DRAXIS, NOA and WP4 leader. The ICT specialists shall familiarize themselves with the RECAP Training Guide and the RECAP platform prior to the Skype meeting. The meeting will have a three-fold objective: i) revise the Training Guide so that concepts are clarified and possible points of misunderstanding regarding the installation of the RECAP platform can be spotted and corrected prior to actual use of the

Training Guides by end-users; ii) instruction of ICT specialists on the installation of the RECAP platform in the selected devices; iii) agreement on the technical support procedure and internal communication.

3.2.3. Adaptation and translation of documents

A number of documents have been produced for the proper development of the Pilot. These include: training guide (D4.2), mailing template for recruitment, informed consent form, guidelines for the organization of the training sessions, attendance sheets for the training sessions, evaluation questionnaires and guidelines for the organisation of focus groups. Adaptation of these documents and translation to local languages is the responsibility of the Pilot organisation in each country. Pilot organisations shall ensure the documents are in accordance with its local/national practices and the regulatory national framework, especially with respect to data protection laws. These documents will be produced as the Pilot is deployed and according to the needs of pilot partners. The training guide is presented as a separate deliverable (D4.2).

3.2.4. Selection of venues and dates for the training

The Pilot team will select the dates and venues for the training of participants in the use of the RECAP platform. Once decided, the selected dates will be communicated to the WP4 leader, project coordinator and technical desk. Different training sessions will be conducted for the different end-user groups in order to facilitate learning. In the case of farmers, given the large number of targeted end-users, training shall be conducted in small groups of maximum 30 participants.

3.2.5. Definition of the time plan for the pilot

The Pilot coordinator at each organization, in collaboration with the other team members, will define the time plan for the Pilot, taking into account the following:

- Availability of the different platform modules (in 2017 and 2018),
- Activities to be conducted according to module,
- Coordination with the CAP season (in the case of Greece, Spain and Lithuania),
- Coordination with inspection activities from relevant bodies (UK),
- Other framework conditions regarding the agricultural system in the specific country will also be considered whenever relevant.

A tentative time plan for the Pilot was presented by partners at the consortium meeting in Pamplona (April 28th 2017). Adjustments to the Pilot time plan shall be communicated to WP4 leader and coordinator as soon as they are foreseen and at the latest every second month (“Pilot update”).

3.2.6. Installation and testing of the RECAP platform sections in the different devices

Once the RECAP platform is available, the ICT specialist/s in each pilot organization will install and test the RECAP platform in the relevant devices of the Pilot organization where training will take place (typically desktop computers). Installation and test of the RECAP platform in the mobile devices (tablets and smartphones) selected by participants in the Pilot will take place during the training session. Installation and test of the RECAP platform in the PCs of the participants in the Pilot will be made by participants themselves following the training guide. Technical support will be readily available at two levels:

- **Local level:** in the Pilot countries, by the ICT specialist/s of the Pilot organization, who will provide participants with contact details for providing technical support,
- **Overall project level:** the ICT specialist/s in each Pilot organisation will receive permanent support throughout the development of the Pilot by DRAXIS and NOA.

3.3. Recruitment of participants: selection and agreements with participants

An independent selection procedure will be set in place to involve participants of each end-user group:

- **Farmers:** partners will select them according to the strategies presented in the proposal (see Chapter 6 for details on farmers' involvement for the specific country).
- **Inspectors:** in the case of Greece and Lithuania, inspectors will be readily reached as they are present in the Pilot organisations. In the case of Spain, the close collaboration with the Department of Agriculture of Navarra ensures they will take part in the Pilot.
- **Agricultural advisors:** in the case of the UK (and Serbia), advisors will be recruited from the local partner organisations.

Whenever possible, participants with the sufficient level of ICT skills and literacy shall be selected for taking part in the Pilot.

For recruitment of participants, Pilot partners will follow the steps presented in the figure below:

Figure 5. Steps for the recruitment of participants for the Pilot

- **Invitation:** the Pilot coordinator will send out a mailing to the pre-selected group of participants for each end-user group. The mailing template will be provided at a later stage and it will have to be adapted to the specific Pilot and translated to the local language. Other tools may be considered for invitation when relevant (see below),
- **Selection:** participants will be selected among the list of interested persons,
- **Signature:** Pilot coordinator will have participants sign the informed consent form,
- **Information:** Pilot coordinator will inform the selected participants on the procedure, timeframe and specific activities of the Pilot and call them to the training session at least one month in advance.

Pilot partners shall also consider the use of any other communication tool and implementation of any other activity that may support the recruitment of participants and the dissemination of the Pilot, including, among others, the preparation of press releases, announcement in the Pilot organisation's magazines, presentation of the Pilot at relevant local meetings, etc. The communication activities foreseen by the Pilot organisation shall follow the Dissemination guidelines defined by the Dissemination manager for the overall project, including the use of pre-defined templates. The person in charge of the communication in the Pilot team shall report to the Dissemination Manager, the WP4 leader and the project Coordinator all communication activities conducted during the preparatory work for the Pilot.

3.4. Summary of pre-pilot activities

The table below presents a summary of the different activities to be conducted as preparatory work for the Pilots.

Table 4. Summary of preparatory work

Task	Brief description	Person/s in charge	Expected achievement date
Setting up of local team	The roles to be covered are: Pilot coordinator, ICT specialist and facilitator.	Pilot coordinator	July 2017
Setting up of internal procedures	Kick-off meeting of the Pilot with Pilot team members	Pilot coordinator	August 2017
	Skype meeting of ICT specialist with WP4 leader and technical desk (DRAXIS and NOA)	Pilot coordinator and ICT specialist	September 2017
	Adaptation and translation of documents.	Pilot coordinator	August 2017
	Selection of venues and dates for the training sessions. Definition of Pilot time plan.	Pilot coordinator	August 2017
	Installation of the RECAP platform in the devices to be used in the Pilot (PCs, tablets and phones). Testing of the proper functioning of the platform.	ICT specialist	September 2017
Recruitment of participants	Invite a pre-selected group of participants in each end-user group.	Pilot coordinator	September 2017
	Selection of target number and signature of inform consent form.	Pilot coordinator	September 2017
	Inform them on the specific date and venue of the training as well as pilot timeframe and foreseen activities.	Pilot coordinator	September 2017

4. PILOT IMPLEMENTATION

Chapter 4 gives a detailed overview of the actual activities to be carried out for a proper implementation of the Pilot. These activities include:

- Training of participants, including the revision of the Training Guides, the organisation of the Training sessions,
- Test of the farmers module of the RECAP platform, which involves the actual piloting of the RECAP platform services with the farmers end-user group,
- Test of the inspectors module of the RECAP platform, which involves the actual piloting of the RECAP platform services with the inspectors end-user group,
- Test of the Paying Agencies module of the RECAP platform, which involves the actual piloting of the RECAP platform services with the Paying Agencies end-user group,
- Monitoring and evaluation of the Pilot activities.

A summary of the activities to be conducted is presented at the end of the Chapter. The foreseen dates of completion of these activities were presented by the Pilot partners at the consortium meeting in Pamplona (April 28th 2017).

4.1. Training of participants

4.1.1. Training of Pilot team in the use of RECAP and revision of the Training Guides

Prior to the organisation of the training sessions, the team at the Pilot organisation will be trained in the use of the RECAP platform through a webinar organised by DRAXIS, in which the WP4 leader and the other partner in the technical desk (NOA) will also participate. The Pilot team will be familiar with the Training Guides so that concepts are clarified and possible points of misunderstanding spotted and corrected prior to actual use of the Training Guides by end-users. WP4 leader will be in charge of revising the Training Guides according to the inputs of Pilot partners. The webinar will also allow ensuring a common understanding of the training sessions' objectives and methodology.

4.1.2. Organization of the training sessions

4.1.2.1. Dates, venues and target groups

As part of the preparatory work, the dates and venues of the training sessions will have been decided by the Pilot team. Participants will be called to the training sessions at least one month in advance (Chapter 3) following the external communication procedures and tools agreed. The organization of the training sessions may vary among Pilot countries according to the Pilot scenarios and the number of end-users targeted. However, it is recommended to organize separate training sessions for each end-user group in order to allow participants to acquire the necessary skills to utilize the relevant modules of the RECAP platform. In the case of farmers, given the large number of targeted end-users, training shall be conducted in small groups of maximum 30 participants.

4.1.2.2. Structure of the training sessions

Training will take place in a single face-to-face session of minimum 3-4 hours duration for each end-user group. The session will follow a hands-on approach in which end-users will directly interact with the RECAP platform. The sessions will be facilitated by staff of the Pilot team: the facilitator and/or the Pilot coordinator, together with the ICT specialist who will be in charge of technical support.

An introductory session will be conducted in each training session, in which participants of each end-user group will be informed on the procedure of the Pilot and will be presented with the flow of activities they will take part in, as shown in the figure below:

Figure 6. Flow of activities for Pilot participants to be presented in the training sessions.

Participants will be provided with a copy of the Training Guide for their personal use, which they will be able to take home after the session. At each training session, participants will be asked to select a username and password for using the platform. This username will be correlated with a tracking number so that the RECAP platform developer will be able to keep track of the information introduced in the platform by each participant. Confidentiality of the information introduced will be ensured by complying with the national and European regulation on data protection, as indicated in the Data Management Plan (D1.2). Participants will have been informed on this extent in the informed consent form.

4.1.2.3. Facilities and reporting

The training venue shall have all facilities required for the training, including individual PCs with the RECAP platform already installed as well as a PC connected to the screen for the trainer. In case the participants bring their own mobile device (tablet and/or smartphone) the ICT specialist should foresee sufficient time to install the RECAP application in the devices prior to starting of the training session. Participants shall sign attendance sheets to prove they take part in the training. The training sessions shall be documented with pictures and, whenever possible, written feedback on the progress of the training session. This information shall be sent to the WP4 leader and the project coordinator at the latest one week after the training session takes place.

4.2. Test of the farmers module of the RECAP platform

The farmers module of the RECAP platform has been designed in order to deliver personalised guidance to farmers on how to comply with cross-compliance regulations, greening measures and other quality standards, such as organic regulations.

According to Pilot country scenario, test of farmers module of the RECAP platform will be conducted differently. In the Greece, Lithuania and Spain scenarios, a representative number of farmers who apply for direct payments (target figures change according to Pilot country) will be asked to input data regarding their fields in the RECAP platform within 1 month after attending the training session and with the use of the profile created in the training session. Test of the farmers module of the RECAP platform will be conducted individually by each farmer on the device of their choice (PC, tablet or smartphone).

In the UK scenario, a representative number of farmers who apply for direct payments will be selected. UREAD and STRUTT & PARKER will gather data through farmers interviews and will input data on individual farms into the RECAP platform. Farmers will also be asked to input the data themselves, observed by UREAD staff, in order to gather feedback on the data inputting process from farmers themselves.

The RECAP platform will provide farmers in Greece, Lithuania, Spain and UK with personalized guidance on how to comply with cross-compliance regulations, instructions on how to prepare for an inspection, a report identifying potential breaches and alerts on identified breaches of cross-compliance. In the UK scenario, the RECAP platform will also provide farmers with opportunities to contact the Farm Advisory System and STRUTT & PARKER agricultural consultants for support.

In the case scenario of Serbia, a representative number of farmers who have organic production will be selected to participate in the Serbian pilot case. The RECAP platform will provide farmers with personalized guidance on how to comply with the regulations of organic soy production, instructions on how to prepare for an inspection, or acquire an adequate organic certificate, accompanied by the description of data they should record or collect in order to minimize the corresponding risks.

Farmers will be able to contact the ICT specialist by e-mail or phone during office hours throughout the Pilot testing of the RECAP platform. Participants will be asked to fill in an evaluation questionnaire (self-administered, most likely in Google forms) after use of the farmers module of the RECAP platform. The RECAP platform coordinator will be able to trace which participants have completed the information remotely and will inform the Pilot coordinator in each country on a weekly basis. Pilot coordinators will send reminders to Pilot participants so that target figures in each Pilot country are achieved.

A preliminary piloting of the farmer's module in the five Pilot countries will be conducted on the functionalities available from September to November 2017. A reduced number of farmers will follow the training session and will test and evaluate the platform so that improvements can be made prior to the full integration of the system (see Chapter 6 for specific details on each country). Testing of the fully integrated RECAP platform by farmers will take place in spring 2018, following the CAP season in Greece, Spain and Lithuania. Planning of the testing of the farmer's module of the RECAP platform in the UK and Serbia is presented in Chapter 6.

The table below presents a summary of the testing of the farmer's module. The table was presented by each Pilot partner at the consortium meeting in Pamplona on April 28th 2017.

Table 5. Detailed planning of testing of farmer's module

Task	Brief description	Dates foreseen	Person in charge
Training sessions (dates and number of sessions)	Organisation of different training sessions with max 30 farmers each. 2017: No of sessions and participants 2018: No of sessions and participants	Both in 2017 and 2018	Pilot coordinator and facilitator
Timeframe of module piloting	Farmer's module will be tested individually by each farmer on the device of their choice. If different modules/functionalities are to be tested (e.g. input of data and appeal), the testing and timeframe should be described for each functionality separately. 2017: No of participants. E.g. 10 farmers for input of data.	Both in 2017 and 2018	Pilot coordinator and ICT specialist

	2018: No of participants. E.g. 120 farmers for input and appeal.		
Evaluation questionnaire	Each farmer fills in self-administered questionnaire within 1 month after piloting	Both in 2017 and 2018 (date above + 1 month)	Pilot coordinator and ICT specialist
Focus Group	A selected number of farmers are invited to a focus group in year 2	Only in 2018	Pilot coordinator and facilitator

4.3. Test of paying agencies module

As per the discussions among Pilot partners and RECAP coordinator, the functionalities of the Paying Agencies module will most likely also be used by inspectors, so they will be tested together with the inspectors' functionalities (see next section).

4.4. Test of the inspectors module of the RECAP platform

The inspectors module of the RECAP platform has been designed in order to reduce the administrative burden of inspectors related to the monitoring of the cross-compliance scheme of the CAP, through an improved remote monitoring of farmers' obligations. According to Pilot country scenario, test of farmers module of the RECAP platform will be conducted differently.

In the Greece, Lithuania and Spain scenarios, the public organisation staff with experience on CAP checks selects the farmers to be advised on CAP compliance and checked (target figures vary according to country scenario, see Chapter 6). Using their profile, inspectors access the RECAP platform and according to the reports produced, they select farmers with higher probability of breach of cross-compliance regulations. They can also increase the number of standards that are checked in the office and can increase the amount of information available to controllers during a field visit. Staff with experience on CAP checks will select a subsample of farms for onsite inspection, and farmers will be consulted with regard to participation in the Pilot process. A number of mock inspections of farms will be undertaken by the authorised personnel in each country (for Spain: DRMAyAL own inspectors, with the support of INTIA's staff; Greece: OPEKEPE inspectors; Lithuania: NMA inspectors) in relation to the cross-compliance regulations, in order to test whether the information gathered through the RECAP application was accurate and representative. The controller who has been assigned to check a specific farmer accesses the information available for the specific field and the report produced by RECAP before performing the on-the-spot check (on a web or mobile application). During the on-the-spot check she/he verifies the report findings, and focuses on issues that need further attention. She/he then submits the control report through the RECAP mobile application.

In the UK scenario, the UREAD and STRUTT & PARKER staff will select a subsample of 25- 50 farms for onsite inspection, and farmers will be consulted with regard to participation in the Pilot. A number of mock inspections of farms (see target number in Chapter 6) will be undertaken by STRUTT & PARKER in relation to cross-compliance regulations in order to test whether the information gathered through the RECAP platform was accurate and representative. During the onsite visit by UREAD and STRUTT & PARKER, the RECAP platform will be used to record information and verify the farmer-submitted data. An inspection report will be submitted through the RECAP mobile application.

Inspectors will test the RECAP platform within the usual period of the CAP season checks and on the device of their choice according to the functionality tested (PC, tablet or smartphone). They will be able to contact the ICT specialist by e-mail or phone during office hours. Participants will be asked to fill in an evaluation questionnaire (self-administered, most likely in Google forms) after use of the relevant module of the RECAP platform. The RECAP platform coordinator will be able to trace which participants have completed the information remotely and will inform the Pilot coordinator in each country on a weekly basis. Pilot coordinators will send reminders to Pilot participants so that target figures are achieved.

The RECAP platform may also be tested by agricultural consultants for delivering support services to farmers in the different pilot cases. In the case of the UK, agricultural consultants, with the consent of the farmer, will access data on the RECAP application and will produce a site-specific and personalised report on how the farmer could increase the productivity of their holdings. External datasets, such as Countryside Stewardship targeting statements, environmental designations, environmental species records, water availability mapping and flood risk mapping, will be used to produce a site-specific and personalised report on how the farmer could increase the environmental productivity / sustainability of their holdings. In addition, the report will link financial and environmental productivity. In the case of Spain, agricultural advisors in INTIA may also test the RECAP platform for delivering advisory service to farmers (see Chapter 6 for details).

A preliminary piloting of the inspector's module will be conducted on the functionalities available from September to November 2017 in all Pilot countries. A reduced number of inspectors will follow the training session and will test and evaluate the platform so that improvements can be made prior to the full integration of the system (see Chapter 6 for specific details on each country). Testing of the fully integrated RECAP platform by inspectors will take place in spring 2018, following the CAP season in Greece, Spain and Lithuania.

The table below presents a summary of the testing of the inspector's module. This table was presented by each Pilot partner at the consortium meeting in Pamplona on April 28th 2017.

Table 7. Detailed planning of testing of inspector's module

Task	Brief description	Dates foreseen	Person in charge
Training sessions (dates and number of sessions)	Organisation of 1 training sessions with the inspectors.	Both in 2017 and 2018	Pilot coordinator and facilitator
Timeframe of module/s piloting	Inspector's module testing will be tested individually by each inspector on the device of their choice. If different modules/functionalities are to be tested (on-line and OTSC), the testing and timeframe should be described for each functionality separately.	Both in 2017 and 2018	Pilot coordinator and ICT specialist
Evaluation questionnaire	Each inspector fills in self-administered questionnaire within 1 month after piloting	Both in 2017 and 2018 (date above + 1 month)	Pilot coordinator and ICT specialist
Focus Group	A selected number of inspectors are invited to a focus group in year 2	Only in 2018	Pilot coordinator and facilitator

4.5. Monitoring and evaluation of the pilot activities

Monitoring and evaluation of the Pilot activities should follow the procedures described in Chapter 2 and it will be conducted by the Pilot coordinator as described in Chapter 3. In a nutshell, the monitoring and evaluation of the Pilot activities to conduct will be the following:

- Update of the KPIs in the BSC in connection with the bi-monthly “Pilot update” email sent by WP4 leader;
- Collection and analysis of the results of the evaluation questionnaires by the different end-user groups;
- Organisation and analysis of the outcomes of the focus groups;
- Preparation of the Pilot Implementation Report in Month 21 (Intermediate Implementation report), including the results of the evaluation questionnaires when available;
- Presentation of the progress of the work in the consortium meetings in Months 19 and 25.
- Preparation of the Pilot Implementation Report and Month 29 (Final Implementation and Evaluation Report), including the results of the evaluation questionnaires and the focus groups;

The Monitoring and Evaluation Chapter of the present Pilot Plan will be updated as the Pilot progresses in order to revise the evaluation questionnaires and include the guidelines for the organisation of the focus groups. This revision is expected to be conducted by spring 2018, prior to the second round of implementation of the Pilot.

5. CLOSURE OF THE PILOT (POST-PILOT)

Chapter 5 gives a detailed overview of the actual activities to be carried out for a proper closure and evaluation of the impact of Pilot. These activities include:

- **Final evaluation of the Pilot**, including compilation and analysis of all the quantitative and qualitative evaluation results of the Pilots in each country,
- **Definition of the exploitation and sustainability of pilot results**, through the production of D4.4 (Final Evaluation Report), D4.5 (Report on procedures followed and lessons learnt) and input of information to WP5 (5.6. Business Models and operational perspective).

A summary of the activities to be conducted is presented at the end of the present Chapter. WP4 leader (INI) will be in charge of carrying out these activities utilising the inputs from Pilot partners, as included in their Final Implementation and Evaluation Reports, and in close collaboration with WP2 leader (UREAD), WP3 leader (DRAXIS) and WP5 leader (ETAM). The foreseen dates of completion of these activities have been estimated on the basis of the deadlines of the respective deliverables.

5.1. Final evaluation of the pilots

5.1.1. Analysis of the quantitative results

The BSC will have been updated for the final time in Month 29 in the Final Pilot Implementation and Evaluation Report, to be sent by Pilot partners to the WP4 leader. Final evaluation of the degree of accomplishment of the target values for the KPIs defined in the BSC will be conducted by WP4 leader at this stage. This will allow:

- Assessing the success of the Pilot development in terms of methodology and procedures followed (output and result indicators), which will be used as input for the production of D4.5 (Report on procedures followed and lessons learnt),
- Assessing the impact of the RECAP platform on the end-user groups (specific figures for the impact indicators obtained in the questionnaires and focus groups whenever possible), which will be used as input for the production of D4.4 (Final Evaluation Report) and the Business Plan in task 5.6.

5.1.2. Analysis of the qualitative results

Information gathered in the questionnaires and focus groups will be analyzed in order to determine: degree of satisfaction of end-users with the RECAP platform, user perceptions, potential demand of the RECAP platform in the Pilot countries, inputs regarding price and purchase of the service, insights for future applications and sustainability of the RECAP platform, transferability issues, potential recommendations in the areas covered by the project as well as policy support scenarios.

5.1.2.1. *Questionnaires*

Analysis of the results of the self-administered questionnaires will be straight forward, as they will be either numeric or graphic rating-scale (still to be determined). Data will be downloaded from Google Forms by the individual Pilot partners, who will be in charge of translating the Excel spreadsheet to English for further processing by WP4 leader. Data will be checked for completeness in order to identify potential sensitive questions that participants were not willing to answer. Statistical analysis will be conducted in the data.

5.1.2.2. Focus groups

Analysis of the results of the focus groups will be conducted, whenever possible, as soon as they take place throughout the Pilot, given that they will be organized with each of the end-user groups as soon as the Pilot testing of the corresponding module/functionality of the RECAP platform takes place. Transcripts of the sessions will be translated to English by the Pilot team, ensuring the translated version includes all necessary information for a good analysis. A Skype meeting among the Pilot partner, the WP4 leader and WP2 leader will be conducted prior to analysis of the results of the focus groups in order to revise the transcripts and avoid misunderstanding of information.

5.2. Exploitation and sustainability of Pilot results

The qualitative and quantitative results gathered in the evaluation of the Pilot will be used for determining the exploitation and sustainability of the RECAP platform with regards to:

- Procedures followed and lessons learnt during the Pilot, as a reference to be used by public organisations and agricultural consultants for future applications of the RECAP platform. This will allow for the production of D4.5 (Report on procedures followed and lessons learnt), which will be a step-by-step manual that will function as a significant tool for the wider take-up of the RECAP platform,
- Input of information to WP5 (5.6. Business Models and operational perspective).

WP4 leader will analyse the available information and data gathered in the quantitative and qualitative tools for producing D4.5 and for providing input to WP5 leader.

5.3. Summary of post-pilot activities

Table 9. Summary of post-pilot activities

Task	Brief description	Person/s in charge	Expected achievement date
Final evaluation of the pilots	Analysis of quantitative results (KPIs in BSC)	INI/UREAD	M29
	Analysis of qualitative results (questionnaires)	INI/UREAD	M29
	Analysis of qualitative results (focus groups information)	INI/UREAD	M29
	Production of D4.4. Final Evaluation Report	INI	M30
Exploitation and sustainability of pilot results	Input to WP5	INI	M29
	Production of D4.5. Report on Procedures and Lessons learnt	INI	M30

6. SCENARIOS AND PILOT CASES IN THE PROJECT COUNTRIES

According to the profile of RECAP partners, the Pilot test of the RECAP platform will be conducted in two different scenarios:

- Public organisations using RECAP to check cross-compliance and inform farmers (Spain, Greece and Lithuania)
- Private agricultural consultants using RECAP to provide services to their customers for complying with EU / national agro-environmental legislation, and quality standards required for specific organic certificates (UK and Serbia).

Chapter 6 presents detailed information on the Pilot scenarios in the different countries.

6.1. Pilot cases featuring cooperation among Public organisations and farmers

In EU countries, farmers who apply for direct payments under the CAP are obliged to comply with cross compliance regulations. The national or regional Payment Agency performs inspection checks on a sample of farmers who have applied for direct payments (inspections are mainly chosen by risk assessment, but there is also a random element). This scenario is going to be tested in Spain, Greece and Lithuania, taking advantage of the participation as project partners of the Greek and Lithuanian Paying Agencies and the regional advisory service on CAP compliance in Spain.

6.1.1. *Spain*

6.1.1.1. *Description of the pilot organization (INTIA) and its role in RECAP:*

The Institute for Agrifood Technology and Infrastructures of Navarra (INTIA) is a public company attached to the Department of Rural Development, Environment and Local Administration (DRMAyAL) of the Government of Navarra. INTIA was born in 2011 integrating existing public companies related to the agri-food sector in Navarra such as the Technical Institute for Agricultural Management, the Technical Institute for Livestock Management, and the Institute for Agrifood Certification. These Institutes had been active on the agri-food development area for more than 30 years. INTIA offers advanced market oriented services for the development of the agri-food sector based on quality, efficiency, innovation and sustainability criteria. One of INTIA's missions is to bring new technologies and innovations to the farmer, such as GIS, Remote Sensing, ICT and process automation. INTIA's staff includes two specialists on the development of web-based decision making tools, support and field models, applied to the development of Alert and Decision Support Systems. Integrated Fertilization of the crops is one of the available tools, based on soil analysis and remote sensing. INTIA has been appointed by the DRMAyAL as the public service responsible for advising farmers on CAP in Navarra.

6.1.1.2. Overview of the Spanish Pilot

Table 10. Overview of the Spanish Pilot.

Pilot Case	Spain
Brief description of the pilot	<p>In the case of Spain inspections are required for specific aids under the Regional Development Programme and aids under the frame of the wine sector (except farmers under the “small farmers scheme”). They are performed by the Inspections Service of the Payment Agency, included in the Department of Rural Development, Environment and Local Administration (DRMAyAL) of the regional Government of Navarra. INTIA, as a public company controlled by the DRMAyAL, provides advisory service for complying with the CAP to over 70% of all farmers in Navarra receiving CAP aids. INTIA has recently set up a WEBGIS platform for providing advisory services to farmers. The RECAP platform would complement the existing WEBGIS platform, allowing INTIA to provide advisory service to farmers on compliance with the cross-compliance scheme.</p> <p>INTIA will conduct the pilot in Navarra, Spain in close cooperation with farmers, cooperatives and with the support of DRMAyAL inspectors for on-the-spot checks. INTIA will pilot test the platform from the public authorities’ perspective, in order to validate how RECAP enables them to monitor the obligations of farmers imposed by the CAP, and increases efficiency and transparency of inspection procedures.</p>
Services evaluated in the pilot	Cross compliance and greening inspections. Advisory services involved.
End-users involved and target number	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Farmers, farmers’ cooperatives: farmers will be reached through the community of farmers already involved in the pilot testing of the sigAGROasesor project (coordinated by INTIA), which aims to develop a web platform offering on-line services to farmers. In addition, farmers will be involved through the Orvalaiz S. Cooperation, which has signed a letter of intent. Its manager is participating in the RECAP advisory board. 35 farmers will be involved in the pilot with a total of 120 CAP claims.
Involvement of other relevant stakeholders	No other stakeholders will be involved.
Other related software	SigAGROasesor, SITUA, SIGPAC.

6.1.2. Greece

6.1.2.1. Description of the pilot organization (OPEKEPE):

OPEKEPE is the Greek National Organization of Agricultural Development and Funding, Control, Orientation and Guarantees for Community Aids and has started its activity in 2001. It is a private legal entity operating for the public interest, supervised by the Minister of Rural Development and Food and has its central offices in Athens. OPEKEPE’s main task is the control and payment of beneficiaries, according to European and national Laws. Every year almost 750.000 beneficiaries benefit approximately 2,7 billion, from community

subsidies. Beneficiaries are mainly farmers and also farmer associations, export companies, investors of the agricultural sector, manufacturing enterprises, etc. OPEKEPE's Board of Directors consists of 11 members. It has its siege in Athens and 6 regional branch directorates and 4 regional units. There are also 39 local offices at Prefecture level. According to its goals, the Agency maintains a comprehensive database with the aforementioned beneficiaries (producers and farmers). In the last 2 years a number of e-services have been funded by EU Regional Funds and developed by OPEKEPE in order to enhance transparency and establish new communication channels with the farmers, reducing bureaucracy, improving cross checks and providing better services to the farmers.

6.1.2.2. Overview of the Greek Pilot

Table 11. Overview of the Greek Pilot.

Pilot Case	Greece
Brief description of the pilot	OPEKEPE, the Greek Paying Agency of Common Agricultural Policy (C.A.P.) Aid Schemes performs Cross Compliance inspections with its own inspectors. OPEKEPE will be responsible for conducting the pilot in Greece, in order to validate how RECAP enables public authorities to monitor the obligations of farmers imposed by the CAP, and increases efficiency and transparency of inspection procedures.
Services evaluated in the pilot	Cross compliance and greening inspections. Advisory services.
End-users involved and target number	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Farmers and farmers' cooperatives will be involved through the Panhellenic Confederation of Unions of Agricultural Cooperatives, which has committed itself to disseminate the project activities to its members and motivate them to engage in the pilot implementation in Greece. 140 farmers will be involved in the pilot.
Involvement of other relevant stakeholders	No other stakeholders will be involved.
Other related software	Link with a) the ministry systems a) "Agricultural Reminders", b): "Livestock Database" etc.

6.1.3. Lithuania

6.1.3.1. Description of the pilot organization (LAAS):

The Lithuanian Agricultural Advisory Service (LAAS) was established in 1993 by the Lithuanian Ministry of Agriculture, Lithuanian Farmers' Union and Lithuanian Association of Agricultural Companies. LAAS functions on two levels: the central level represented by the Head Office and the regional level represented by district advisory offices in each district of the country (48 offices in total). The department specialists of the LAAS Head Office take care of in-service training of consultants, provide them with training materials, help them to carry out purposeful planning of their activities, provides regular monitoring of the implementation of their work plans and quality of services, develops new services and advisory tools (software), participate in the international projects and different national and international work groups.

LAAS has established a farmers’ advisory system covering the whole country. Company employs 400 employees, who improve their skills in Lithuania and abroad on regular basis. Each year about 18.000 farmers and rural dwellers uses LAAS services or participate in trainings, organised by LAAS consultants. Approximately 5.000 of them have signed contracts and use the LAAS services during the whole year. About 85-90 % of them have contracts with LAAS for more than a year. 43 % of these contracts are made with young farmers (up to 40 years old). Up to 15 % of these contracts are made with new clients.

LAAS provides advisory and training services on issues relevant to the environment, crop production, cattle breeding, engineering, works safety, forestry and economics/ farm accounting areas. A large proportion of these activities is directly connected to the Rural Development Programme (RDP 2007-2013 and 2014-2020) and the CAP challenges.

LAAS is a certified advisory institution, part of the national Farm Advisory System (FAS), which provides advisory services and helps farmers to evaluate and improve their activity in the implementation of Cross Compliance requirements. During the period 2009 – 2014, LAAS advisors made more than 3.500 farm assessments (farm checks) on their compliance of cross-compliance requirements, provided more than 60.000 hours of advisory services.

LAAS has the extensive experience not only on providing services for farmers. LAAS acts in different international programs (Baltic Sea Regional Program, ERASMUS+, Interreg, Nord Plus), professional networking (GFRAS, EUFRAS www.eufRAS.eu), and collaborations with national and international partners. On recent years LAAS is more orientated to create new e-services for farming over international (EIP from RDP) and international (Horizon 2020, Erasmus+, Interreg) cooperation.

6.1.3.2. Overview of the Lithuanian Pilot

Table 12. Overview of the Lithuanian Pilot.

Pilot Case	Lithuania
Brief description of the pilot	<p>NMA, the National Paying Agency under the Ministry of Agriculture, performs inspection checks on a sample of 5% of farmers who have applied for direct payments in Lithuania with its own inspectors. On average, 4.500 inspections are made every year. The Lithuanian Agricultural Advisory Service (LAAS) is a public institution the mission of which is to help all farming people to develop their businesses profitably without causing damage to environment, produce competitive production, survive and be leaders under the conditions of market economy. It has established a national farmers’ advisory system.</p> <p>LAAS will be responsible for pilot testing the RECAP platform in Lithuania, in order to validate how it enables public administration to provide to farmers advisory services on their compliance with the CAP requirements.</p>
Services evaluated in the pilot	Cross compliance and greening inspections. Advisory services.
Target groups involved and target number	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Farmers, farmers’ cooperatives will be involved through the Lithuanian Association of Agricultural Companies, which is one of the founders of the Lithuanian Agriculture Advisory Service (project partner LAAS). 150 farmers will be involved in the pilot.
Involvement of	No other stakeholders will be involved.

other relevant stakeholders	
Other related software	No other platforms.

6.2. Pilot cases featuring cooperation among private agricultural consultants and farmers

Farmers who apply for direct payments under Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) support schemes or payments under certain Rural Development Programme for England (RDPE) schemes are obliged to comply with cross compliance regulations. The Rural Payments Agency (RPA) performs inspection checks on a sample of at least 1% of farmers who have applied for the Basic Payment Scheme (BPS) in England (inspections are mainly chosen by risk assessment, but there is also a random element). Approximately 1.700 cross compliance inspections are carried out in England annually.

6.2.1. UK

6.2.1.1. *Description of the pilot organization (STRUTT & PARKER):*

STRUTT & PARKER is one of the largest organisations of agricultural consultants and land managers in England. It is a privately-owned commercial organisation which manages 800,000 hectares of land for farmers, public organisations and the United Kingdom government. Its agricultural consultants advise farmers on cross-compliance, the Basic Payments Scheme and the Common Agricultural Policy, and have a highly detailed knowledge of how the schemes and inspection regimes work. It also has an in-house research team which supports the agricultural consultants. The research team has reviewed, condensed and simplified guidance on the new Common Agricultural Policy from the United Kingdom government and paying agency, the Rural Payments Agency, for farmers. It has also developed a simple tool for farmers to use in applying the new Common Agricultural Policy which allows them to plot what crops and ecological focus areas they need in order to meet national requirements. The tool has been very successful and has been downloaded over 5,000 times.

The organisation also provides other services to farmers, including determining farm strategy, managing farm workers, managing farming agreements, budgeting, cropping, livestock and grassland management and cost control. They arrange grain sales and manage all documentation relating to the Common Agricultural Policy. The organisation also assists farmers in applying for entry into agri-environment schemes and other grant funding. All our consultants have direct farming experience.

6.2.1.2. *Overview of the UK Pilot*

Table 12. Overview of the UK Pilot

Pilot Case	UK
Brief description of the pilot	STRUTT & PARKER main tasks in the proposal are to (i) identify users' needs (WP2), and (ii) to deploy and operationalise the pilot plan, in particular to identify, recruit and survey farmers taking part in the pilot plan in UK (WP4). Its profile matches these tasks as: (i) it provides advice to farmers on cross compliance and so understands their needs, and (ii) it can recruit farmers from its own clients using its brand recognition.
Kind of services evaluated in the	Agricultural services to farmers for complying with CAP regulations, and increasing the environmental productivity / sustainability of their holdings.

pilot	
Target groups involved and target number	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Farmers & land managers and National Farmers’ Union, Rural Payments Agency and other Competent Control Authorities; Environment Agency, Natural England, Veterinary Medicines Directorate & Animal and Plant Health Agency, Agricultural consultants and Farm Advisory System, 50 advisors. STRUTT & PARKER, one of the largest organizations of agricultural consultants and land managers in England will engage its own clients using its brand recognition. 100 farmers will be involved in the Pilot.
Involvement of other relevant stakeholders	National Farmers’ Union, Farmers Weekly magazine, possibly Red Tractor Assurance.
Other related software	Within the project, at least investigate the format of data records exportable from commercial farm management database software (Muddy Boots, Gatekeeper, etc.) (e.g. CSV files) and the compatibility with the RECAP platform databases (e.g. field parcel reference numbers).

6.2.2. Serbia

6.2.2.1. *Description of the pilot organization (INO):*

InoSens doo (INO) is an innovative company, founded as **spin-off of the University of Novi Sad** with the mission to accelerate the transfer of **innovative ICT technologies to the agri-food sector**. The value proposition of INO builds equally upon technological excellence and business innovation. INO is engaged in **design and development of sensors**, deployment of **Wireless Sensor Networks** and application of **advanced remote sensing techniques** for optimizing economic performance and environmental sustainability **in agriculture**. The INO team has long-term experience in projects that incorporate a high degree of technical challenge and therefore require high expertise and innovative approach. The company combines the higher-level scientific profile of its staff with advanced management skills to successfully take up all the phases of a project’s lifecycle (study-design-implementation-operation). INO builds on key accounts from the **agri-food sector in the broader Balkans region** and maintains strong and lasting alliances with complementary players (e.g. hardware vendors, agronomists, food scientists etc.). In RECAP, INO will be responsible for the pilot testing of the platform in Serbia with the scope to provide it to agricultural consultants and developers for creating their own added value services for farmers, taking advantage of the data available, and extending the functionality of the platform.

6.2.2.2. *Overview of the Serbian Pilot*

Table 13. Overview of the Serbian Pilot.

Pilot Case	Serbia
Brief description of the pilot	<p>Serbia became a EU candidate country in 2012, and began accession negotiations in 2014. As such, the country is committed to transpose and implement the <i>acquis</i> on agriculture and rural development by the date of accession.</p> <p>The Directorate for Agrarian Payments is the main (but as of yet not only) public organ</p>

	<p>administering direct payments and national rural development subsidies. The establishment of the agency represents a milestone in the adoption of <i>acquis</i>. It will eventually assume sole responsibility for agricultural payments in the country, and is responsible for implementing the upcoming Instrument Pre-Accession Assistance in Rural Development (IPARD) during the accession process.</p> <p>Standard area payments disbursed by the Directorate for Agrarian Payments do not have conditions comparable to cross compliance. Breaches of environmental protection measures prescribed by law can be legally sanctioned but are not linked to withholding payment of agricultural subsidies. On-spot controls of area payments are conducted by the Agricultural Inspection Service, yet the control rates officially remain as low as 2% for certain measures.</p> <p>The only area payments disbursed by the Directorate for Agrarian Payments with conditions akin to CAP – in regards to (i) conditioning subsidies to encourage environmental stewardship and (ii) having a systematic and effective monitoring – are subsidies to support organic agriculture. The Strategy for Agriculture and Rural Development of the Republic of Serbia 2014-2024 (Official Gazette RS 85/2014) recognizes that organic agriculture contributes to rural development and conserving the environment. To protect the environment, organic agriculture restricts management options, mirroring several CAP restrictions: limits to fertilization, mandatory buffer strips, etc. Compliance with regulations is required at the risk of strict sanctions, and established monitoring systems are considered generally effective. In Serbia, organic certification is annual, and requires certification of production quantities, as an extra control mechanism. This process is conducted by organic certification agencies, and agricultural consultants are often hired for support. The Law on Organic Production (Official Gazette RS 30/2010) was drafted to fully align with EU regulation on organic farming (Regulation EC 834/2007).</p> <p>The weak point in the process for organic subsidies lies in estimating upcoming production quantities that have to be declared on organic certificates. This creates an opportunity for malfeasance that is hard to spot and avoid, creating a large risk for diverting subsidies from supporting the sector. The heavily export-oriented sector is seen as a strategic one by the government, and has been exponentially growing in the past decade in part due to continued and growing public support.</p>
<p>Services evaluated in the pilot</p>	<p>In Serbia, the RECAP platform will support the entire process of subsidy provision for organic farmers, certification agencies, agricultural consultants and for the public authorities tasked with implementing, managing and controlling this payment scheme.</p> <p>In addition, by supporting a subsidy program of the Directorate for Agrarian Payments with similarities to CAP, the RECAP platform will be positioned to support monitoring aspects of relevant subsidies within IPARD. One of IPARD’s stated objectives in to provide assistance for the implementation of the <i>acquis</i> concerning the CAP.</p>
<p>Target groups involved and target number</p>	<p>INO is a founding member of PA4ALL, a Living Lab for Precision Agriculture based in Vojvodina, which has access to more than 3,500 users from the entire farming value chain of the region, including farmers, vendors of equipment and agrochemicals and agronomists/ consultants. This community is already involved in a number of EC funded activities (e.g. the Future Internet accelerator FRACTALS) and will be the starting point to engage users in the Serbian pilot.</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ministry of Agriculture and Environmental Protection of the Republic of Serbia
<p>Involvement of other relevant stakeholders</p>	<p>The Serbian Pilot case is focused on organic agriculture, with organic certification bodies, organic farmers and public bodies to overlook that certification is in line with legal requirements.</p> <p>During our previous activities with RECAP (tasks 2.2 and 2.3) we have already established firm relations with organic associations and certification bodies in Serbia. Thus, we engaged them for feedback and to identify relevant requirements. As such, they are integrated in the design of the pilot as a key stakeholder group.</p> <p>We have engaged government bodies (Sector for Quality Control of the Ministry of Agriculture and Environmental Protection) to understand their workflows in regards to monitoring the organic sector. These processes are highly administrative in nature and focused on paper work. We recognize that public monitoring of yield/quantity estimations (Serbia's certification process applies to land and a quantity of annual yield) are limited. RECAP in this pilot will provide a tool to address this problem, providing public monitoring with an evidence-based means to control certified quantities on paper vs actually produced quantities. As a result, the government will be able to monitor the entire process more efficiently and with fewer administrative processes.</p>
<p>Other related software</p>	<p>No existing software will be integrated into RECAP. However, geo-referenced data (e.g. farm coordinates) will be used. This data will be entered manually, once cadastral numbers from farmers are obtained.</p>

6.3. Detailed timeframe of the Pilot cases per country

Months	2017				2018									
	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30
COUNTRY	S	O	N	D	E	F	M	A	M	J	JL	A	S	O
Spain						C			OL, OS					
Greece	OL, OS					C			A	OL, OS				
Lithuania	OL, OS, R	A, R	A, R	C				A	A	OL, C	OS, C, R		R, C	C
UK	IT, IF			I, OS, R, C, IF	OS, R, C, IF		OS, R, C, OL, IF	R, C, OL, IF	C, OL, IF	OL, IF				
Serbia							Serbia Pilot							

Spain, Greece & Lithuania Scenario

Application by farmers
On-line inspections by PA
On-site inspections by PA
Report submission by PA
Control/appeal by farmers

A
OL
OS
R
C

UK Scenario

Data input by RECAP Pilot team
Data input by farmers
On-line inspections by consultants
On-site inspections by consultants
Report submission by consultants
Control/appeal by farmers

IT
IF
OL
OS
R
C

Figure 6. Time plan of the different Pilot scenarios.